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FROM CONSUMERISM TO THE PRINCIPLES OF SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY: POSSIBLE OPTION OR NECESSITY

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Abstract. Consumerism is one of the most striking socio-economic phenomena of modernity, influencing both the structure of capitalist economies and the way in which individuals define their identity and social relationships through the act of consumption. From its roots in the Industrial Revolution to contemporary digital forms, consumerism has evolved through a complex process marked by significant economic, political and cultural changes. This article approaches the concept of consumerism from a multidimensional perspective (economic, sociological, cultural and critical) and outlines the main stages of its historical development, drawing on the specialized literature. The analysis also focuses on the effects of excessive consumption on natural resources, pollution, climate change and socio-economic inequalities, with an emphasis on the vulnerabilities of the Republic of Moldova. The findings highlight the close link between consumption patterns, environmental degradation and systemic economic risks, emphasising the importance of the transition to a circular economy and the adoption of sustainable consumption practices.

Keywords: consumerism, social identity, digitalisation, mass consumption, natural resources, circular economy.

Introduction

Consumerism is defined in the specialized literature through a significant diversity of interpretations, which highlights the complexity of this phenomenon. From a general perspective, consumerism represents a socio-cultural and economic reality specific to industrialised societies, manifested through the tendency to constantly acquire goods and services in ever-increasing volumes. Whereas in the past consumption was primarily geared towards meeting essential needs, in contemporary society it has taken on new dimensions, becoming a practice that reflects not only economic aspects but also cultural values, social relationships and elements of person-

al identity.

The marketing dictionary describes consumerism as a structured and institutionalised social movement involving citizens, public authorities and non-governmental organisations, with the aim of strengthening the rights and influence of buyers in relation to sellers. Essentially, this constitutes a collective reaction to the abuses and lack of accountability possible in the marketing process. On the one hand, the phenomenon is expressed through the active and conscious attitude of consumers, and on the other hand, through the interventions of consumer protection organisations, professional associations and public authorities, aimed at combating unfair practices in the market.

Researchers have identified at least three distinct conceptual dimensions of consumerism:

1. *The economic dimension*: Consumerism refers to economic policies that emphasise consumption as the engine of economic growth, arguing that consumers' freedom of choice should decisively guide firms' production decisions.

2. *The social movement dimension*: Consumerism refers to the body of organised activities by governments, businesses and independent organisations, aimed at protecting and strengthening consumers' rights in their dealings with producers and sellers.

3. *The socio-cultural and ideological dimension*: Consumerism is understood as a socio-economic order and a value system that glorifies the continuous acquisition of goods and services, transforming consumption into a means of constructing identity and social status [1].

Consumerism is defined both as a societal and economic framework in which the purchase of goods and services is prioritised and praised, and as a social movement that seeks to enhance the rights and power of buyers in relation to sellers [2,3]. An important issue is the concept of „universal identity”; consumerism offers individuals across the globe the idea that they are defined, first and foremost, as „consumers”. In the digital age, this has evolved into digital consumerism, a paradigm that examines the balance between consumer empowerment (access to information, reviews) and consumer vulnerability (misinformation, privacy risks) [3].

The circular economy is gaining increasing popularity, especially in developed countries, and is a complex concept that encompasses a multitude of different aspects. Thus, the circular economy can be defined as a model of production and consumption that involves the sharing, renting, reusing, repairing, renovating, and recycling of existing materials and products for as long as possible [4].

Its emergence is determined by multiple existential challenges, which endanger the very existence of humanity. Linear development according to the principle of consume, throw away is no longer sustainable, and problems related to ecology, quality of life, etc., progress at an alert, threatening pace, which requires drastic and audacious measures. In this context, the circular economy where materials never become waste and nature is regenerated could be a solution and can tackle climate change and other global challenges, like biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution, by decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources [5]. Thus, the characteristic measures of the circular economy are diverse and can be developed at the level of the enterprise or industry, the national economy or at the level of international regulation. All of these represent a complex interconnected system depending on the specifics of the business sector, national and international programs, policies and strategies. Companies, consequently, must identify the most appropriate solutions for their business to be able to comply with the principles of sustainable development [6].

The history of consumerism: origins and evolution

A defining notion in the evolution of consumerism is the „consumer revolution”, in his book *The Birth of a Consumer Society*. McKendrick’s research shows that in 18th-century England there was a rapid and widespread increase in the consumption of consumer goods, an event preceding the Industrial Revolution, which matched massive demand with nascent industrial supply. This was the first documented manifestation of mass consumption, extending beyond the elites to involve the emerging middle classes [1]. However, in *Archiv für Sozialgeschichte*, criticises the stage-based models that restrict the origins of consumer society to the 20th century, highlighting that practices, transnational flows and cultures of consumption with much older roots shaped modern Europe. The author emphasises that traditional theories no longer offer sufficiently robust explanations for understanding this complex history [2].

The Industrial Revolution of the 18th–19th centuries marked a turning point in the evolution of consumerism, transforming it from a phenomenon specific to the elites into mass consumption. Mechanised production and technological advances significantly reduced the price of goods, making products accessible that were previously reserved for the privileged classes. The textile industry was the first sector to systematically implement the mass production of clothing.

Rapid urbanisation, the consolidation of the middle class and the emergence of department stores laid the foundations for the infrastructure

of modern consumption. The public display of products stimulated social imitation and the phenomenon of „propulsive envy”. American historiography of the consumer movement identifies, three major waves of reform, later expanded to four [7].

The first wave (1900–1914) developed according rapid rapid industrialisation and scandals relating to the quality of food and medicines. Investigative journalists exposed unsanitary production conditions to the public, which generated political pressure for regulation. As a result, the Food and Drug Act and the Meat Inspection Act were passed in 1906, the first US federal consumer protection laws. This phase was characterised by public outrage, investigative journalism and targeted legislative intervention.

The second wave (1920–1960) emerged consequently of the consumer boom of the 1920s and the subsequent economic crisis. Consumer credit in the US reached \$7 billion, and massive advertising created a constant desire for goods and services. The economic crash of 1929 and the Great Depression fostered a critical consumer awareness of abusive market practices, and the founding of Consumers Union in 1936 institutionally strengthened the defence of consumer rights, transforming consumerism into an organised social movement.

The post-war consumer society (1945–1960) was characterised by rapid economic growth and the emergence of mass consumerism. Post-war America was built as a „consumer republic”, where consumption was no longer merely a personal indulgence, but a „civic responsibility” and a driver of collective prosperity. Economic leaders, trade unions, government agencies and the media promoted the idea that satisfying the desire for „more, newer and better” was, in fact, every citizen’s contribution to national well being. Consumption was granted moral legitimacy and associated with the values of liberal democracy.

The third wave (1960–1980) focused on consumer rights and protective legislation. Triggered by President Kennedy’s message on consumer rights, this wave generated extensive legislation on product safety, consumer protection, food labelling and the environment. The state played a central role in safeguarding consumer rights, but by the late 1970s, consumer activism began to lose ground in the face of a business counter offensive and the Reagan administration’s deregulation policies.

Contemporary consumerism has its origins in the „*Charter of Consumer Rights*” proposed on 15 March 1962 by US President John F. Kennedy. Thus, 15 March 1962 marks the historic moment of the birth of the global consumer movement, and is now celebrated as International Consumer Day [8].

The decades of neoliberal globalisation, spanning 1980 to 2000,

marked a distinct phase of geographical expansion and intensification of consumerism. An emerging transnational capitalist class spread consumerist practices to developing countries through the influence of the mass media and the expansion of multinational corporations, often without taking into account these states' capacity to produce autonomously or to afford the imposed consumption.

Analysis in the *Cambridge Transactions of the Royal Historical Society* highlights a fundamental shift: whilst the classical consumer society prioritised access to basic goods, globalised consumerism has emphasised individual freedom of choice as a central value, whilst simultaneously diminishing the political and collective agenda of the consumer movement.

The fourth wave of consumerism (2000–present) centres on the digital revolution. The internet has redistributed power between producers and consumers, providing access to comparative information, reviews, social networks and online advocacy tools. This period is characterised by the digitalisation of consumer activism, including practices such as boycotting and buycotting facilitated by social platforms, and by the challenges posed by the platform economy [9]. Recent research shows that digital movements, such as the #DeleteUber or #GrabYourWallet campaigns, combine modern forms of mobilisation with traditional issues of platform capitalism.

At the same time, ethical and sustainable consumerism is also emerging, introduces the concept of „consumer citizenship” as an integrative approach that combines the protection of consumer rights with responsibility towards environmental sustainability and the resources of future generations.

The impact of consumerism on the environment

The rapid expansion of global consumption in recent decades has profoundly altered the relationship between society and the environment. The prevailing economic model, geared towards mass production and intensive consumption, has led to the excessive use of natural resources, increased pollution and the exacerbation of phenomena associated with climate change. Small and highly vulnerable countries, such as the Republic of Moldova, are affected to a greater extent by these processes, as they depend to a significant extent on natural resources, have institutions with limited capacity to intervene, and an underdeveloped environmental infrastructure.

Consumerism is the main driver of the overexploitation of natural resources — minerals, timber, water and fossil fuels. Global material extraction has tripled since 1970, reaching 95.1 billion tonnes in 2019 and 104 billion tonnes in 2024. This escalation places immense pressure on ecosys-

tems, leading to habitat destruction, biodiversity loss and resource depletion [10]. The extraction and processing of natural resources account for more than half of total global greenhouse gas emissions and approximately 40% of fine particulate emissions — a type of pollution that is particularly harmful to human health. Furthermore, the extraction and processing of resources account for over 90% of terrestrial biodiversity loss [11]. The water consumption of the fast-fashion industry illustrates the impact of consumerism: manufacturing a single cotton T-shirt requires 2,700 litres of water, equivalent to a person's water consumption over 2.5 years. The entire textile industry consumes 141 billion cubic metres of water annually. Globally, food production utilises over 40% of the Earth's habitable land area and accounts for 70% of total freshwater consumption [12]. The fast fashion industry perfectly illustrates the destructive impact of consumerism. Textile consumption in the EU has risen from 17 kg per person in 2019 to 19 kg in 2022, whilst 12 kg of clothing per person is discarded annually. Globally, the fast fashion industry: [13]

- Accounts for 10% of annual global carbon emissions — more than aviation and international shipping combined,
- Generates 92 million tonnes of textile waste every year,
- Releases 500,000 tonnes of synthetic microfibres into the oceans annually, simply through washing clothes — the equivalent of 50 billion plastic bottles,
- It is the second-largest consumer of water among industries worldwide [14].

Consumerism generates colossal amounts of waste. In 2024, 220 million tonnes of plastic waste were produced globally, the equivalent of 28 kg per person. Of this, 69.5 million tonnes were mismanaged and ended up in the natural environment. It is estimated that currently 75 to 199 million tonnes of plastic are found in the oceans, with the potential for plastic to outnumber fish by 2050 [15].

The Republic of Moldova is highly vulnerable, largely due to its heavy reliance on agriculture and the excessive use of natural resources. Forests cover approximately 11% of the country's land area, a level considerably lower than the European average, which stands at around 30% [16]. This situation contributes to soil erosion, increasing the risk of flooding and landslides. The agricultural sector consumes very large quantities of water, accounting for approximately three-quarters of the total water resources used nationally. At the same time, the country faces a significant degree of pollution of both surface and groundwater, which negatively affects public health and economic efficiency, particularly in rural areas.

The Republic of Moldova is facing a waste management crisis. According to data from 2024, there are 1,131 landfill sites in the country, covering 1,225 hectares of land. Half of all waste ends up in sites that do not meet minimum environmental standards, and 90% of municipal waste is „managed” exclusively through long-term landfill, posing a direct threat to soil, air and groundwater [17,18].

The Republic of Moldova is among the states highly exposed to the effects of climate change, phenomena largely intensified by the global model of excessive consumption. Agriculture, considered the central pillar of the national economy, is increasingly affected by frequent droughts, torrential rains and unpredictable temperature variations, which jeopardise the stability of agricultural production and food security.

On a global scale, consumerism also contributes to the exacerbation of social inequalities. The manufacture of cheap goods often relies on the use of labour from countries with weak labour laws, low wages and precarious working conditions. At the same time, the negative environmental impact of mass consumption - such as air pollution, water contamination and land degradation - disproportionately affects vulnerable populations, who live near sources of pollution and have limited resources for protection and adaptation.

Paradoxically, a consumption-oriented lifestyle does not deliver the level of satisfaction and happiness it promises. Psychological studies indicate that people who place particular importance on the accumulation of material goods tend to exhibit higher levels of depression and anxiety and to be less socially engaged compared to those who promote non-materialistic values. Thus, excessive consumption fuels a vicious circle of constant dissatisfaction, sustained by constant social comparisons and the constant influence of advertising.

The European Union’s 8th Environment Action Programme aims to significantly reduce the consumption footprint by 2030 and keep the impact within planetary boundaries. However, between 2010 and 2023, the EU’s consumption footprint increased by approximately 5%, and projections indicate a further increase by 2030 unless decisive action is taken. The consumption sectors responsible for over 70% of the EU’s aggregate impact are housing, food and household goods [19,20].

The main obstacles to reducing consumption-related emissions include the absence of uniform monitoring systems, the complexity of global supply chains and the lack of effective coordination between countries.

The importance of the transition to a sustainable economy in the context of environmental challenges

Contemporary society is facing significant challenges determined by traditional consumption patterns. In this sense, consumerism constitutes one of the most harmful patterns of excessive consumption, which has become widespread due to the increase in incomes for larger segments of the population. A solution that can be imposed as a viable alternative, which would create sustainable prospects, is the circular economy that promotes the efficient use of resources. This model focuses on the reuse, recycling and regeneration of materials, thus requiring a change in the way consumers and companies approach products and services.

The principles of the circular economy such as waste reduction, reuse, recycling contrast sharply with consumerism in which there is a strong tendency to produce and purchase new products, without considering the impact that this has on the environment. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a complex, multilateral transition both in the way products are designed and consumed. Thus, if the linear economic model generates major problems related to the storage and disposal of waste, affecting the quality of the environment, by implementing the principles of the circular economy, waste is transformed into a valuable resource that can be reintegrated into new manufacturing processes that would ensure the development of new businesses and reduce the risks of environmental pollution [21].

A fundamental, but probably the most complex, element of this transition is the transformation of the mentality of consumers and producers. Education and awareness about the benefits of product reuse, moderate consumption or sharing services is a key element in this regard. The environmental education must be promoted at an early age by including it in educational curricula, but also later through their appropriate development. The principles of the circular economy must be studied not only within formal education, but also in continuing education, included in the business environment so that they accept the transition to a new economic model. This requires a constant effort from government institutions and civil society, which can only have an effect in the long term. Indeed, there is a rather long distance from the perception that resources are unlimited, the desire for excessive consumption to a sustainable approach, which would take the environment into consideration.

Education can and should include creating a culture of reuse, for example by promoting „vintage” stores, which would encourage consumers to buy already used products, thus reducing the demand for new products, exchange programs: initiatives that facilitate the exchange of products between consumers or sharing platforms that would allow the use of a product by several people.

It should be emphasized that the education of the principles of sustainable economy must be strengthened with legislative initiatives. The implementation of the principles of circular economy may require considerable costs, at the first stage, for which additional financial or other incentives are necessary. An imperative is the alignment of the legislative framework of the Republic of Moldova with international regulations, primarily the EU, which is a mandatory condition for accession. In the context of the worsening ecological situation, environmental regulations are becoming increasingly strict, and the experience of EU countries is one of the most advanced in the world and can be an important benchmark for the development of the circular economy for our country. Adopting a circular model not only reduces the costs related to waste management and the purchase of new raw materials, but also, due to financial or other incentives, can constitute an essential competitive advantage. Also, companies that are promoters of the principles of sustainable economy can benefit from access to European funds and create a favorable corporate image. Therefore, alignment with EU environmental regulatory requirements becomes a strategic opportunity for Moldovan companies to position themselves as responsible organizations both on the local and international market. This can have a positive impact on the environment and provide favorable economic results, but can also contribute to increasing consumer and investor confidence, forming a sustainable development perspective.

The new legislation must stimulate investments in green technologies, to determine investors to develop their businesses according to the principles of the circular economy, but it is also necessary to create a robust infrastructure that allows sorting and recycling of materials. In this context, the intervention of the government is necessary, which would develop the infrastructure either from its own resources or as a result of collaboration between the public and private sectors. Public-private partnerships can facilitate the development of policies and strategies that support the circular economy, to support innovation and the design of products and production processes in accordance with the principles of sustainability.

The transition from a linear to a circular economy is a very complex process, also from a technological point of view. It involves a complete redesign of both the production and consumption cycle, starting from reducing waste and transforming it into raw materials for other production processes and to reuse and revitalize products after their consumption. Therefore, the transition to a circular economy requires a complex and radical adaptation of companies, major investments in research and development, as well as the adoption of business models based on sustainability that have proven

their efficiency [22]. Companies must be encouraged through various instruments to invest in green technologies, technologies for the reuse of materials, and to develop strategic partnerships. Green investments can favor the creation of completely new industries and the considerable reconfiguration of existing ones, also technological innovations can lead to significant cost reductions in the long term. The objective of government institutions is to create a prolific and sustainable ecosystem formed by institutions with multilateral regulation based on the principles of the circular economy, proactive NGOs, sustainability-oriented enterprises and research institutions, universities that would have as their objective the development of circular technologies and business models. We have to underline, that efforts to develop advanced recycling technologies, digitalization of supply chains and monitoring of material flows ensure a much more efficient use of resources, increase productivity and ensure greater efficiency of companies' activities, and in a dynamic economic environment, the capacity for innovation through the lens of sustainability of companies becomes the essential pillar for adaptability, increased competitiveness and upward development [23].

The transition from consumerism to a circular economy is a very complex process and determined by high initial costs, but also possible resistance to change. For the successful implementation of these reforms, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive set of measures at different levels such as: legislative, educational, including financial and other incentives, developing public-private partnerships, conducting research oriented towards sustainability, etc., thus it would be possible to create a circular ecosystem oriented towards increasing the quality of people's lives.

Conclusions

Global consumerism is generating a systemic crisis with three interdependent dimensions: ecological, social and economic. Although the Republic of Moldova contributes relatively little to global consumption, the negative effects are felt disproportionately: poor waste management infrastructure, pollution of water resources, heightened climate vulnerability and the degradation of natural capital. Existing solutions include implementing the circular economy, regulating consumption and setting prices that reflect the true environmental cost, alongside a profound shift in cultural values relating to consumption. The transition to sustainable production and consumption models, supported by technological innovation and behavioural changes, is crucial for protecting the environment and ensuring long-term economic stability.

In a society dominated by excessive consumption and waste of re-

sources, the responsibility of consumers, companies and the entire society becomes a determining factor of long-term success. The circular economy develops a mindset that puts sustainability, ethics and equity at the forefront, contributing to the creation of an environment in which the well-being of the individual, communities and the environment is indispensable. By reducing pollution and ensuring efficient management of resources, creating new jobs in green industries, a new foundation is laid for economic development oriented towards sustainability and harmonization. The approach that includes extended social responsibility ensures both the improvement of the quality of life, but also ensures social cohesion, reducing inequalities. The circular economy, therefore, represents a bridge between economic progress and the environment, ensuring that development is carried out in harmony with social and ethical values.

The effective implementation of the circular economy requires concerted efforts. These include collaboration between all stakeholders, consumer education, creating incentives for companies and creating a favorable framework for innovation and circular transition. Adopting the circular economy is not only a benefit for the environment, but also for the economy, offering opportunities for innovation and growth in various areas such as recycling, reuse or responsible design, and the application of these principles can radically transform today's consumer society.

Sustainable economic models can ensure a balance between economic development and technological progress on the one hand and environmental protection and quality of life on the other. It is the responsibility of everyone: public institutions, companies or each individual to actively support and promote the circular transformation, so that economic prosperity and a favorable environment are propelled together.

In conclusion, we have to underline that the transition to a sustainable economy effectively responds to the major challenges of the contemporary era such as excessive consumption, depletion of natural resources and respectively the worsening of the environmental situation. The circular economy, due to its complexity, represents a profound change in the economic paradigm, in which each resource and each process is redesigned to maximize its value and minimize the negative impact on the environment. Therefore, adopting a circular economic model is essential to respond to the current major challenges, and proactive environmental policies, changing the way of production and consumption, investments in green technologies are important components in terms of sustainable development. A concerted effort is needed from all stakeholders to achieve the circular transformation, to promote effective collaboration between the public, private and civil

society sectors, this being a mandatory condition to ensure a perspective in which economic development is achieved based on a balance between prosperity and environmental protection, ensuring resources for future generations and a favorable environment for human existence.

Bibliography:

1. Meenu Mahajan. Consumerism: A Globalization Concept. In: International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development. Volume: 2, Issue: 9, 245-248 Sep. 2015 www.allsubjectjournal.com e-ISSN: 2349-4182 p-ISSN: 2349-5979. <https://www.allsubjectjournal.com/assets/archives/2015/vol2issue9/73.pdf> (accessed 02.02 2026).

2. Bodislav D., Georgescu R. Consumerism and capitalism: dynamic evolution, economic benefits, and ethical challenges. In: Theoretical and Applied Economics. Volume XXXII (2025), No. 1(642), Spring, pp. 251-266. <https://store.ectap.ro/articole/1820.pdf> (accessed 02.02 2026).

3. Park H., Lee J. Discourse analysis of online product reviews: A discussion of digital consumerism and culture. In: Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace, 13(2), article 4. 2019. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5817/CP2019-2-4> (accessed 02.02 2026).

4. Economia circulară: definiție, importanță și beneficii. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/ro/article/20151201STO05603/economia-circulara-definitie-importanta-si-beneficii> (accessed 12.01 2026).

5. Circular economy introduction. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy-introduction/overview> (accessed 12.01 2026).

6. Crucerescu C. Economic paradigms and business models to achieve the sustainability of companies. In: USV Annals of Economics and Public Administration, 2020, vol. 20, nr. 2(32), pp. 72-80. ISSN 2285-3332.

7. Brobeck S. The Fourth Great Wave of Consumer Reform. ACCI Esther Peterson Lecture. In: Consumer Interests Annual Volume 60, 2014. Consumer Interests Association (ACCI) archive (accessed 22.01 2026).

8. Chiriac L., Rusu V. Ambalajul în relație cu protecția consumatorului. In: *Conferința Tehnico-Științifică a Colaboratorilor, Doctoranzilor și Studenților*, Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei, 16-18 noiembrie, 2017. Chișinău, 2018, vol. 2, pp. 513-516. ISBN 978-9975-45-543-5. ISBN 978-9975-45-545-9 (Vol.2). <http://repository.utm.md/handle/5014/521> (accessed 22.01 2026).

9. Munteanu T. Modele conceptuale și metodologii aplicative în strategia marketingului digital. In: Marketingul și Logistica în era Digitală: Sem-

inar Științific Național, Chișinău, Republica Moldova, Ediția a II-a, 23 Mai, 2025. Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei. Chișinău: UTM, 2025, pp. 164-168. ISBN 978-9975-64-555-3 (PDF). <https://doi.org/10.52326/mled2025.23>. <https://repository.utm.md/handle/5014/33144> (accessed 22.01 2026).

10. How Does Overconsumption Affect Resource Depletion? <https://pollution.sustainability-directory.com/question/how-does-overconsumption-affect-resource-depletion/> (accessed 25.01 2026).

11. EEA: Understanding the data — what drives our material footprint? <https://ieu-monitoring.com/editorial/eea-understanding-the-data-what-drives-our-material-footprint/444027> (accessed 25.01 2026).

12. Environmental Impact of Fast Fashion Statistics (2025). <https://www.uniformmarket.com/statistics/fast-fashion-statistics> (accessed 25.01 2026).

13. Fast fashion: EU laws for sustainable textile consumption. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20201208STO93327/fast-fashion-eu-laws-for-sustainable-textile-consumption> (accessed 26.01 2026).

14. Fast Fashion and Its Environmental Impact in 2026. <https://earth.org/fast-fashions-detrimental-effect-on-the-environment/> (accessed 26.01 2026).

15. Plastic Pollution in The Ocean – 2025 Facts and Statistics. <https://www.beautyofplanet.com/plastic-pollution-in-the-ocean-2025-facts-and-statistics/> (accessed 26.01 2026).

16. Mîrza S. Ecomarketing: suport de curs. Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei, Facultatea Inginerie Economică și Business, Departamentul Teorie Economică și Marketing. Chișinău: Tehnica-UTM, 2025, 200 p. ISBN 978-9975-64-504-1. <http://repository.utm.md/handle/5014/29322>

17. Moldova Faces Severe Waste Management Crisis: Infrastructure Lags Behind Public Willingness. <https://dontwasteit.hu/en/gemini-said-moldova-faces-severe-waste-management-crisis-infrastructure-lags-behind-public-willingness/> (accessed 25.01 2026).

18. Bogdanova S. Влияние технологических инноваций на «зеленую» логистику и эко-маркетинг. In: Marketingul și logistica în era digitală: Seminar științific național, dedicat aniversării 60 de ani al UTM, 18 octombrie 2024. Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei, Facultatea Inginerie Economică și Business, Departamentul Teorie Economică și Marketing. Chișinău: Tehnica-UTM, 2024, pp. 13-18. ISBN 978-9975-64-481-5 (PDF). <http://repository.utm.md/handle/5014/28743>

19. Consumption footprint (based on life cycle assessment) in Europe (2025). <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/consumption->

footprint-based-on-life (accessed 25.01 2026).

20.4.7 Global impacts from EU consumption. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/europe-environment-2025/thematic-briefings/circular-economy-and-other-enablers-of-transformative-change/global-impacts-from-eu-consumption> (accessed 25.01 2026).

21. Bugaian L., Gheorghîța M., Ciloci R., Crucerescu C., Țurcan I., Diaconu C. *Economie Circulară: Note de curs*, Chișinău, 2023, Editura „Tehnica-UTM”, ISBN 978-9975-45-992-1.

22. Gheorghîța M., Oberșt, A. Advancing sustainable development through environmental commitment of apparel producers. In: *Journal of Social Sciences*, 2021, vol. 4, nr. 1, pp. 47-57. ISSN 2587-3490. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2021.4\(1\).06](https://doi.org/10.52326/jss.utm.2021.4(1).06)

23. Țurcan I., Țurcan R., Stratila A. Digitalization and its role in the development of circular economy business models. In: *Competitiveness and sustainable development*, Ed. 5, 2-3 noiembrie 2023, Chișinău. Chișinău: „Tehnica-UTM”, 2023, Ediția 5, pp. 103-109. ISBN (pdf) 978-9975-64-364-1